

THE FACTORS AFFECTING EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AT BINH THUAN GENERAL HOSPITAL, VIETNAM

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Abstract

The study evaluates factors affecting employee satisfaction at Binh Thuan General Hospital. Through theoretical research and actual survey of employee satisfaction at Binh Thuan General Hospital, research results show that, with secondary and primary data collected from 441 survey questionnaires, Observing workers at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital, the study identified five factors that positively impact the job satisfaction of workers at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital including: 1) Training, evaluation and promotion; 2) Workplace relationships; 3) Salary and benefits; 4) Nature of work and 5) Working conditions. In addition, using T-test and ANOVA to test the difference in satisfaction according to personal characteristics shows that employee satisfaction also differs based on age, level, age, and working experience at Binh Thuan General Hospital.

Keywords: Employee Satisfaction, Binh Thuan General Hospital, JSS model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is one of the essential factors that attracts the attention of organizations as well as researchers. The 4.0 industrial revolution and globalization have affirmed the importance of the knowledge economy and the increasing competition for human resources. In that context, improving employee job satisfaction is a top priority for human resource managers. Health care is a particular industry in terms of professional qualifications, working environment, and nature of work. Binh Thuan General Hospital is also facing a turning point when implementing a plan to upgrade the hospital from type 2 to type 1 by 2028. To achieve this goal, in addition to the government's and hospitals' attention, all levels also need the government's consent and the consent of all officers and employees working at the hospital. Therefore, workers' job satisfaction at the hospital is an essential factor in improving the quality of medical examination and treatment, completing assigned work targets and achieving the goal of upgrading the hospital. Many domestic and foreign studies suggest that it is necessary to create job satisfaction for workers. When job satisfaction increases, workers will be motivated to work more actively, leading to higher productivity and efficiency. According to Abdelkarim (2017), unhappy workers will lead to low productivity, affecting physical and mental health. Employees satisfied with their jobs are less likely to change jobs and quit. Therefore, this study was formed to find factors affecting workers' job satisfaction at Binh Thuan General Hospital and propose solutions. With data from actual surveys and data processing and analysis, this study provides health sector managers with more insight into employee job satisfaction to orient appropriate policies in effectively using human resources to achieve the organization's common goals.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Job satisfaction is considered an emotional state brought about by the evaluation and attitude of employees while performing work. Job satisfaction represents a feeling that occurs when employees perceive their work to help them achieve their physical and mental needs (Aziri, 2011). Spector (1997) also believes that job satisfaction is how employees express their attitudes about work and other aspects of work, which brings employees to express the degree to which they like or dislike their work and do not like their job. According to Hoppock (1935), job satisfaction is a combination of psychology, physiological circumstances, and work environment, affecting employees during work performance. The most common and popular factors that impact employee job satisfaction are the nature of work, salary, benefits, working facilities, and promotion opportunities (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2007; Adams, 1963; Smith et al., 1969; Spector, 1997). Agyepong et al. (2004) identified factors affecting job satisfaction: working environment, salary, equipment, promotion opportunities, lack of housing, tax benefits, and training programs. Luddy (2005) identified two more factors that affect the job satisfaction of medical workers: the nature of work and relationships with colleagues. On the other hand, Leshabari et al. (2008) also discovered another main factor affecting the job satisfaction of medical workers: facilities.

In Vietnam, some authors also put forward some concepts of job satisfaction: Do Huu Nghi et al. (2015) said that job satisfaction is generally considered an emotional state due to the employee's evaluation and attitude while performing the job or the results of the job. Doan Thi Thuy Hai and Nguyen Thi Ngoc Mai (2020) argue that job satisfaction is generally defined as the degree to which workers like their work, which is an attitude based on their perception (positive or negative) about the job or work environment.

Nature of work: is the job content that matches the employee's abilities, inspiring the employee to develop his or her abilities. Appropriate work arrangements will exploit workers' potential, increase labor productivity, and make them comfortable. In other words, workers will feel satisfied with their assigned work if that job matches their abilities. Research by Ha Nam Khanh Giao and colleagues (2019), Pham Thu Hang, Pham Thi Thanh Hong (2015), and other studies also show the positive influence of the nature of work on employee satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis H1 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H1: The nature of work has a positive influence on employee job satisfaction

Working conditions are related to aspects of work such as a comfortable workplace, ensuring lighting and temperature, and a clean working space. These factors affect job satisfaction because workers always want a more comfortable working environment. In other words, workers with good working conditions will have high job satisfaction and vice versa. Research by Tran Kim Dung (2005), Turyilmaz et al. (2011), Ha Nam Khanh Giao et al. (2019), and Nguyen Thi Thuy Linh (2019) shows the positive influence of working conditions on employee satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis H2 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H2: Working conditions have a positive influence on employee job satisfaction

Wages and benefits play an essential role in ensuring and contributing to improving the material and spiritual life of workers, thereby promoting increased labor productivity and growth. Increase satisfaction and satisfaction in their work. In Vietnam, studies also show a positive relationship between salary, benefits, and job satisfaction of workers such as Tran Kim Dung (2005), Nguyen Thi Thu Hang, Nguyen Khanh Trang (2013), and Nguyen Tien Thuc (2018). Therefore, hypothesis H3 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H3: Salary and benefits have a positive influence on employee job satisfaction.

Relationships with colleagues affect overall job satisfaction since workers usually interact and work together. The main factors of co-worker satisfaction are trust, dedication to work, helping each other at work, friendliness, and fair competition for rewards and promotions within the organization. In other words, workers will feel more satisfied with their jobs with good relationships with colleagues. Many studies prove that good relationships with colleagues will enhance workers' job satisfaction, such as Pham Thu Hang, Pham Thi Thanh Hong (2015), Nguyen Tien Thuc (2018), and Turyilmaz et al. (2011). Therefore, hypothesis H4 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H4: Relationships with colleagues have a positive influence on employee job satisfaction

As an employee's manager, the superior or leader gives employees satisfaction through communication, showing concern, fair treatment, and recognition of employee contributions. In other words, relationships with superiors (leaders) positively affect employee satisfaction with work. Many studies have clarified this, such as research by Belias and Koustelios (2014), Le Nguyen Doan Khoi, Nguyen Huu Nghi (2014), and Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2018). Therefore, hypothesis H5 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H5: The relationship with superiors has a positive influence on employee job satisfaction

Training and promotion are shown by employees being given training opportunities to improve their job skills and the possibility of them being promoted to higher positions. Workers will feel satisfied with jobs that give them training opportunities and help them advance their careers. Therefore, creating training and promotion opportunities will make employees feel satisfied with their jobs. Studies by Jun et al. (2006), Turyilmaz et al. (2011), Singh (2013), and Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2018) also show that training and promotion have a positive impact on job satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis H6 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H6: Training and promotion have a positive influence on employee job satisfaction

Job performance evaluation assesses the employee's job performance compared to established standards. Job performance evaluation helps confirm the capacity and ability of employees. Job performance evaluation is the basis for helping organizations determine bonus levels and evaluate employees' future advancement abilities. When employees are evaluated according to their abilities, they will feel satisfied. On the contrary, the employee will feel satisfied if the performance evaluation is only formal and high and does not reflect the actual contribution.

Therefore, hypothesis H7 is stated as follows:

Hypothesis H7: Job performance evaluation factors have a positive influence on overall employee satisfaction

Some studies have shown that the relationship between gender, educational level, and work seniority affects job satisfaction. Frempong et al. (2018) and Dhir et al. (2020) showed that a strong relationship exists between workers' demographic characteristics and their job satisfaction (Abdelkarim, 2017). Therefore, hypothesis H8 is presented as follows:

H8: There is a difference in job satisfaction based on personal factors

The research model is inherited and developed by using a combination and selection of a number of theoretical bases and research factors of previous scientific researchers.

Figure 1: Research framework

3. METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in four steps: Step 1: Initial qualitative research, Step 2: Preliminary quantitative research, Step 3: Official quantitative research, and Step 4: Additional qualitative research.

After determining the research model, the author conducted discussions with two experts in human resources, five managers, and ten workers to build a scale suitable for empirical research hospital movements. Discuss using a preliminary scale set concerning job satisfaction factors from previous studies. Discussion participants are free to give their opinions on job satisfaction. As a result, all workers participating in the discussion agreed with the proposed scale. The measurement questions are easy to understand and are not duplicated. The scale and its sources are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Scale and its sources

Variables	Items	Code	Sources
Nature of work	I'm always busy with work	BCCV1	Huang et al. (2007)
	I have the ability to work independently	BCCV2	
	I have the opportunity to do different jobs	BCCV3	
	I can do many things that do not go against my conscience	BCCV4	
	Work gives me stable employment	BCCV5	
	I have the opportunity to develop my abilities	BCCV6	
	I have the opportunity to advance at work	BCCV7	
	I feel accomplished in my work	BCCV8	
Working conditions	The hospital where I work is very safe	DKLV1	Swamy et al. (2015)
	The hospital where I work is clean and airy	DKLV2	
	I am provided with full equipment to support my work.	DKLV3	
	My working equipment is very modern	DKLV4	
Salary and benefits	I am having a satisfactory income from work	TLPL1	Huang et al. (2007)
	My current salary is commensurate with my working capacity	TLPL2	
	Employee remuneration policies (salaries, bonuses...) are fair	TLPL3	
	I am rewarded commensurate with my contributions and contributions	TLPL4	
	I receive a fair reward when I complete the job well	TLPL5	
Relationships with colleagues	I feel comfortable working with my direct manager.	QHDN1	Aur et al. (2011).
	I am satisfied with the process of exchanging and providing internal information	QHDN2	
	My colleagues are comfortable and pleasant	QHDN3	
	Colleagues are always ready to help me in my work	QHDN4	
	My colleagues and I work well together	QHDN5	
Relationship with superiors	My supervisor always listens to employees' opinions	QHCT1	Loi et al. (2012). Hart et al. (2014)
	My superiors always show friendliness and respect for workers	QHCT2	
	My achievements were recognized and evaluated promptly by my superiors	QHCT3	
Training and promotion	Evaluate job performance fairly	DGCV1	Tran Kim Dung (2005)
	Evaluate job performance in accordance with the employee's job performance results	DGCV2	
	The evaluation process is clear and serious	DGCV3	
	Evaluate work performance to ensure openness and transparency	DGCV4	
	Evaluate work performance to ensure effectiveness	DGCV5	
Job performance evaluation	I am fully trained to do my job effectively	DTTT1	Reddy et al. (2019)
	The hospital has a clear employee training and	DTTT2	

	development plan		
	The hospital always encourages and creates many opportunities for advancement and development of employees	DTTT3	
	The hospital has a fair training and promotion policy	DTTT4	
Job satisfaction	I am satisfied with what I achieve at work	HL1	Braun, et al. (2013).
	I feel satisfied with the comfort of working at the hospital	HL2	
	I always consider the hospital as my second home	HL3	

To consider and evaluate the respondents' attitudes, in this case, job satisfaction, the researcher can choose the type of questions in his questionnaire. A closed-question format means that the questionnaire designer will always provide answer options with statements about the respondent's attitude, such as strongly agree, agree, not sure, disagree, completely agree, or totally disagree.

Data were analyzed and processed using SPSS 22.0 software, using the following methods: descriptive statistics, testing scale reliability using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, and exploratory factor analysis. After the regression step, the study performed ANOVA and T-test analysis to test the difference between the demographic variables and employee satisfaction.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1 Statistical results of demographic characteristics of the research sample

The study was conducted on 450 samples in January 2024 at Binh Thuan General Hospital. There were 441 valid questionnaires, accounting for 98% of the ballots issued. The descriptive statistical results of the sample are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: descriptive statistical of the samples

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	129	29.3	29.3	29.3
	Female	312	70.7	70.7	100.0
Working experiences	Under 3 years	66	15.0	15.0	15.0
	Over 10 years	219	49.7	49.7	64.6
	From 3 - 5 years	82	18.6	18.6	83.2
	From 5 - 10 years	74	16.8	16.8	100.0
Position	Managers	42	9.5	9.5	9.5
	Workers	399	90.5	90.5	100.0
Education	Undergraduate & Postgraduate	258	58.5	58.5	58.5
	College	166	37.6	37.6	96.1
	High school or lower	17	3.9	3.9	100.0
Age	Under 25 years old	0	0	00.0	00.0

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	129	29.3	29.3	29.3
	Female	312	70.7	70.7	100.0
Working experiences	Under 3 years	66	15.0	15.0	15.0
	Over 10 years	219	49.7	49.7	64.6
	From 3 - 5 years	82	18.6	18.6	83.2
	From 5 - 10 years	74	16.8	16.8	100.0
	26 - 35 years old	231	52.4	52.4	52.4
	36 - 45 years old	118	26.8	26.8	79.1
	Over 45 years old	92	20.9	20.9	100.0

Table 2 shows the statistical results describing the characteristics of the study sample as follows:

Regarding gender, out of 441 people surveyed, 312 were women, accounting for 70.7%, and 129 were men, accounting for 29.3%.

Regarding working experience, the number of people surveyed with less than three years of work is 66, accounting for 15%; from 3-5 years is 82, accounting for 18.6%; from 5-10 years is 74, accounting for 16.8%; and over ten years there are 219, accounting for 49.7%.

Regarding the educational level of the people surveyed, the results showed that 258 people had university and postgraduate degrees, accounting for 58.5%, and 166 people had college and intermediate degrees, accounting for 37.6%. At the high school level or lower, 17 people accounted for 3.9%.

Regarding the age of the surveyed workers, the results showed that there were no people under the age of 25, 231 people from 26 to 35, accounting for 52.4%, 118 people from 36 to 45, accounting for 26.8%, and 92 workers over the age of 45, accounting for 20.9%.

4.2 Reliability and exploratory factor analysis

The Cronbach's Alpha analysis results show that all the observed variables have Corrected Item-Total Correlation greater than 0.3 and Cronbach's Alpha more significant than 0.7, indicating reliability. These variables are used in further EFA analysis.

Table 3: Exploratory factor analysis

	1	2	3	4	5
DG2	.806				
DG4	.797				
DG5	.796				
DT3	.785				
DG3	.780				
DT4	.770				
DG1	.754				
DT2	.726				
DT1	.622				

CT3	.610	.508			
DN4		.866			
DN5		.846			
DN3		.828			
DN1		.682			
DN2		.652			
CT2		.609			
CT1		.608			
TL2			.853		
TL1			.851		
TL4			.827		
TL3			.744		
TL5			.665		
BC2				.728	
BC3				.700	
BC4				.645	
BC8				.620	
BC5				.599	
BC6				.553	
BC7				.516	
DK4					.615
DK3					.613
DK2					.593

The factor analysis process is carried out through 4 testing steps: (1) The factor loading coefficients of the observed variables are all greater than 0.5, proving that these observed variables are reliable and valid. Considered to have practical significance (Hair et al., 1998); (2) KMO coefficient = 0.948 > 0.5 satisfies the appropriateness of factor analysis if $0.5 \leq \text{KMO} \leq 1$ (Hair et al., 1998) (Quoted by Trong and Ngoc, 2008); (3) Sig coefficient. = 0.000 < 0.005 of the Bartlett test indicates that there are observed variables that are statistically significantly correlated with each other in the population, so the observations are suitable for factor analysis; (4) Cumulative variance = 72.662%, meaning 72.662% of the total variance is explained by the factors and according to Gerbing and Anderson (1988), this cumulative variance is greater than 50% which is appropriate for analysis factor.

After performing the tests, the next step is to perform factor rotations to ensure that the observed variables belong to the factors, have factor loadings greater than 0.5, and are evenly distributed across the factors.

Factor analysis results show that five factors (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5) formed from 32 observed variables from the original 34 observed variables; the observed variables are closely correlated. Next, the new factors will be renamed due to the disturbance of the observed variables after performing the factor rotation. The new factors are named as follows:

- Factor H1 is formed from 9 observed variables (DGCV2, DGCV4, DGCV5, DTTT3, DGCV3, DTTT4, DGCV1, DTTT2, DTTT1) of the factors Job Performance Evaluation and Promotion Training, so it is named re: "Training, evaluation and promotion."

- Factor H2 is formed from 8 observed variables (QHCT3 QHDN4, QHDN5, QHDN3, QHDN1, QHDN2, QHCT2, QHCT1) of the factors Relationship with colleagues and Relationship with superiors, so it is renamed: "Workplace Relationships."
- Factor H3 is formed from 5 observed variables (TLPL2, TLPL1, TLPL4, TLPL3, TLPL5) of the factor Salary and benefits, named "Salary and benefits."
- Factor H4 is formed from 7 observed variables (BCCV2, BCCV3, BCCV4, BCCV8, BCCV5, BCCV6, BCCV7) of the factor Nature of work, so it is named "Nature of work."
- Factor H5 is formed from 3 observed variables (DKLV4, DKLV3, DKLV2) of the Working Conditions variable named "Working Conditions".

4.3 Correlation analysis

The test results show that the highest "Correlation coefficient" between the variable Job satisfaction of employees and other factors is 0.708, and the lowest is 0.550. These relationships are significant when sig < 0, 05. These independent variables can be included in the model to explain the dependent variable.

Table 5: Results of correlation analysis

	HL	BCCV	DKLV	TLPL	MQH	DT-DG-TT
HL	1					
BCCV	.654**	1				
DKLV	.617**	.513**	1			
TLPL	.634**	.454**	.645**	1		
MQH	.550**	.493**	.411**	.431**	1	
DT-DG-TT	.708**	.592**	.589**	.573**	.741**	1
** p< 0.01						
*p< 0.05						

4.4 Hypothesis testing

The author uses a multiple regression model to evaluate factors' impact on the satisfaction level of workers at Binh Thuan General Hospital. From the results of the above factor analysis, it was determined that 5 factors affect the level of satisfaction of workers at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital with their current job.

These are the five explanatory variables included in the corresponding symbolic regression model: X1- Nature of work, X2- Working conditions, X3- Salary and benefits, X4- Workplace relationships, X5 - Training, evaluation and promotion and employee job satisfaction are the dependent variables denoted Y. The regression model is written as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5$$

Table 6: Multiple regression of factors affecting employee satisfaction

Model	Unstandardized regression coefficients		Standardized regression coefficients	T	Sig.	VIF
	B	Standard error	Beta			
(Constant)	.003	.133		.023	.982	
BCCV	.345	.044	.287	7.807	.000	1.673
DKLV	.110	.036	.125	3.070	.002	2.044
TLPL	.216	.036	.233	5.921	.000	1.908
MQH	.027	.046	.025	.591	.555	2.254
DT-DG-TT	.327	.053	.312	6.184	.000	3.135

$R^2 = .647$; $R^2_{\text{adjusted}} = .643$; $F = 159.694$; $(P = 0,000)$

The F-test (ANOVA analysis table) shows the significance level of sig. = 0.000 < 0.05 (with F value = 159.694). Thus, the regression model is suitable for the whole population. These five independent variables affect workers' job satisfaction at Binh Thuan General Hospital, ensuring a reliability of over 95%.

The study is based on the tolerance of the variable (Tolerance) and the VIF coefficient to detect the phenomenon of multicollinearity. The regression analysis results using the Enter method show that the variance magnification factor VIF is less than ten and the tolerance of the variable (Tolerance) is more significant than 0.1, so the hypothesis that the model is multicollinear can be rejected.

The regression analysis results show that four research hypotheses, H1, H2, H3, and H5, have a significance level < 0.05 and should be accepted. Hypothesis H4 has a significance level > 0.05, so it is not accepted.

The testing of research hypotheses shows that the factors of nature of work, working conditions, salary and benefits, training and promotion, and job evaluation positively impact the job satisfaction of workers at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital. The regression equation showing the influence of factors in the model is built as follows:

$$HL = 0,287*BCCV + 0,125*DKLV + 0,233*TLPL + 0,312*DTDGTT$$

From the regression model, it can be seen that the factor with the most substantial impact on employee satisfaction is the Training - Evaluation - Promotion factor with $\beta = 0.312$; this means that if the Training - Evaluation activity is Price – If a hospital's promotion is 1 unit better, employee satisfaction will increase by 0.312 units. Ranked second is the Nature of Work factor with value $\beta = 0.287$, which means that if the Nature of Work is 1 unit better, employee satisfaction will increase by 0.287 units. Ranked third is the factor Salary and Benefits with the value $\beta = 0.233$, which means that employee satisfaction will increase if the hospital's salary and benefits increase by 1 unit is 0.233 units. Ranked last is Working Conditions with the value $\beta = 0.125$, the factor with the lowest influence on employees' job satisfaction at Binh Thuan General Hospital.

Table 7: Results of testing differences in satisfaction according to personal characteristics

	Method	P value	Results
Gender	<i>t-test</i>	$P>0.05$	No difference
Experience	<i>ANOVA</i>	$P<0.05$	Difference
Location	<i>t-test</i>	$P>0.05$	No difference
Level	<i>ANOVA</i>	$P<0.05$	Difference
Age	<i>ANOVA</i>	$P<0.05$	Difference

Three out of five demographic variables have differences in job satisfaction; ANOVA results show that people with more extended work experience (over ten years) are more satisfied than the remaining age groups (under ten years). The ANOVA results also show that people with lower qualifications are more satisfied with their jobs than highly qualified people. In contrast, older people have higher levels of job satisfaction than younger people.

4.5 Discussion

Research results show that four factors affect job satisfaction at Binh Thuan General Hospital. In which the Training - Evaluation - Promotion factor has the most substantial impact, this result shows that employees are interested in self-development, affirming their role and position in the organization, and their needs seek self-affirmation. This result is consistent with the characteristics of medical human resources, and the survey participants are trained and have degrees. The nature of work ranked second among the factors affecting job satisfaction in this study, similar to many previous studies. It further confirms that medical human resources need to be trained and implemented by the training major to develop capacity and increase job satisfaction. The two factors, Salary, Benefits, and Working Conditions, have the level of influence ranked 3rd and 4th, respectively, among the four factors that affect the job satisfaction of workers at Binh Thuan General Hospital as well as is a remarkable result. For Western research, the job evaluation model is often rarely mentioned (Belias & Koustelios, 2014). However, most studies on satisfaction show working conditions as the first impacted factor (For example, Turyilmaz et al. (2011) and Sumitha and Padmaja (2015)). Previous studies have considered working conditions and the working environment as factors, including tangible and intangible elements (corporate culture); however, this study considers working conditions from a physical perspective. This finding is quite interesting in dividing satisfaction by material and spiritual factors. Job satisfaction from the spiritual aspect has a more substantial impact than the material one. This result is somewhat different from previous studies such as Mai Thu Phuong et al. (2018), Nguyen et al. (2018), and Ha Nam Khanh Giao (2018). Salary, benefits, and working conditions are often factors with a greater influence on employee job satisfaction.

Besides, the t-test and ANOVA test results show three qualitative variables belonging to the demographic characteristics of workers that show differences in their satisfaction, including age, work experience, and qualifications. People with more years of experience will be more satisfied, while people with low qualifications show higher satisfaction than those with college or university. Similar results are also found in Frempong et al. (2018) and Dhir et al. (2020).

5. CONCLUSION AND MANAGEMENT IMPLICATIONS

The study's objective is to evaluate the impact of factors on the job satisfaction of workers at Binh Thuan General Hospital. Through theoretical research and actual survey of employee satisfaction at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital, research results show that, with secondary and primary data collected from 441 survey questionnaires, Observing workers at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital, the study identified four factors that positively impact the job satisfaction of workers at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital including: 1) Training – Evaluation & Promotion; 2) Nature of work; 3) Salary and benefits; 4) Working conditions. In addition, using t-tests and ANOVA to test the difference in satisfaction according to personal characteristics shows that employee satisfaction also differs based on the length of time spent working at the hospital, age, and education level of workers.

Training - Evaluation - Promotion is the factor that most substantially impacts employee satisfaction, so Binh Thuan General Hospital needs to have policies on training, job performance evaluation, and promotion. Be more proactive, positive, and flexible with employees working at the hospital. Hospitals need solutions and policies to encourage employees to attend school to improve their professional qualifications. Regularly open or send staff to participate in short-term training courses for medical staff to improve their qualifications and update new knowledge about examination and treatment activities directly taught by sound experts.; Encourage medical staff, specifically doctors and nurses, to participate in scientific research activities and attend conferences. At the same time, most opinions say that salary is the most vital influencing factor to job satisfaction and is the leading cause of brain drain in human resources at Binh Thuan General Hospital; this study helped make a logical statement with the characteristics of human resources. The medical profession is a trained, qualified workforce, and they need to be recognized for their role in the organization and promote personal development along with the development of the hospital. Of course, the results of training to improve the quality of human resources are also associated with improving the quality of job performance, and the results of job performance evaluation are associated with the salary, bonus, welfare regime, and career advancement roadmap of an employee's career. Therefore, hospitals pay attention and invest in human resource training and accurately evaluate and record the capabilities and contributions of workers.

In addition, the hospital also needs to focus on ensuring good salaries, allowances, and benefits by the provisions of law and supplement reward regimes for employees such as bonuses for employees with good performance initiatives, improvements in work, scientific research rewards, outstanding collectives and individuals during the year, and in emulation campaigns based on specific achievements. Hospitals must pay attention to improving working conditions and giving employees the best working conditions to improve employee job satisfaction. Especially with the medical industry's specific working environment, minimizing labor risks and ensuring labor safety and hygiene must focus on improving and upgrading working equipment (medical equipment) and applying digitalization to reduce unnecessary work.

Despite theoretical and practical contributions, the research still has certain limitations. For example, the survey sample was only conducted at Binh Thuan Provincial General Hospital, representing other hospitals needing consideration. However, the JSS model is widely used in research in many fields and countries. However, further research needs to analyze and develop a more suitable model for Vietnam's conditions and the characteristics of a medical unit. Besides, the multivariate linear regression method can provide a picture of the impact of factors, but further studies need to implement more reliable methods, such as CB_SEM, to test and determine the results of this study.

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